

Description of EERIE atmosphere-only reference simulations

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Executive Summary

This report describes the EERIE atmosphere-only reference simulations, including an overview of the experimental design, model configurations, and data availability. These simulations are conducted with two resolutions of the IFS (~28 km and ~9 km) and HadGEM3 (~60 km and ~20 km) atmosphere models. Ocean and sea-ice boundary conditions are specified using high-resolution satellite-based estimates of daily-mean sea surface temperatures (SST) and sea-ice concentration from the European Space Agency Sea Surface Temperature Climate Change Initiative (ESA CCI SST version 3.0) and the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT) Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility (OSI-SAF), respectively. Other than their treatment of ocean and sea-ice boundary conditions, the higher-resolution configurations of IFS and HadGEM3 described here are scientifically identical to the atmosphere components of the corresponding EERIE coupled simulations (IFS-NEMO/IFS-FESOM, HadGEM3-UM-NEMO). A preliminary evaluation indicates that EERIE atmosphere-only simulations accurately capture long-term trends and interannual variability in key climate metrics (e.g. global mean 2m temperature and net TOA radiation balance), which partly reflects the strong constraint from the specified SST boundary conditions. An exploratory Lagrangian composite analysis of ~25 km and ~9 km IFS simulations indicates that both configurations have sufficient horizontal resolution to capture a local atmospheric response to SST anomalies associated with ocean mesoscale eddies. These experiments will be used in combination with EERIE coupled simulations and other idealised atmosphere-only experiments to provide insights into the impacts of ocean coupling, atmospheric resolution, and the role of the ocean mesoscale for weather and climate variability.

1 Introduction

One of the goals of the EERIE project is to understand the local and remote impacts of sea surface temperature (SST) gradients and variability associated with ocean boundary currents and mesoscale eddies on atmospheric weather and climate variability. This work will draw on multiple lines of evidence, including the eddy-rich EERIE coupled simulations, which have much higher horizontal resolution than typical multidecadal climate simulations. However, increasing the horizontal resolution of the ocean component of a coupled model impacts many aspects of the coupled system, including (i) the mean state of the ocean and atmosphere, (ii) the magnitude and timescales of ocean-atmosphere variability and air-sea interactions, (iii) the properties and statistics of ocean eddies, and (iv) the position and associated SST gradients of western boundary currents (e.g., Roberts et al. 2016; Siqueira and Kirtman, 2016; Roberts et al. 2018; Small et al. 2019; Moreno-Chamarro et al, 2021). The atmospheric response in a given location to a change in ocean resolution will therefore reflect the combined impact of many processes, including the response to both local and remote changes in the ocean mean state and/or variability.

This report describes a series of atmosphere-only reference simulations, which are intended to complement the EERIE coupled simulations (deliverable 4.1) and, in combination with idealised atmosphere-only experiments (deliverable 9.4), help us to disentangle the impact of the ocean mesoscale on weather and climate variability. Simulations are conducted with two resolutions of the IFS (~28 km and ~9 km) and HadGEM3 (~60 km and ~20 km) atmosphere models with ocean and sea-ice boundary conditions specified using high-resolution satellite-based estimates of daily-mean sea SST and sea-ice concentration. Other than their treatment of ocean and sea-ice boundary conditions, the higher-resolution configurations of IFS and HadGEM3 described here are identical to the atmosphere components of the corresponding EERIE coupled simulations (IFS-NEMO/IFS-FESOM, HadGEM). The experiments described in this report are summarised in Table 1.

These reference simulations will serve several purposes within the EERIE project and beyond, and will enable the following activities:

- The EERIE atmosphere-only simulations are conducted at two horizontal resolutions, which provides an opportunity to evaluate the impact of horizontal resolution on atmospheric processes.
- Comparison of the EERIE atmosphere-only simulations with the eddy-rich EERIE coupled simulations will provide insights into the impacts of ocean coupling and SST biases.
- The reference atmosphere-only simulations described here will serve as control experiments for the idealised simulations with modified SST boundary conditions described

in deliverable 9.4. Together, these experiments will provide a clean framework to evaluate the atmospheric response to mesoscale SST features in the EERIE models, including the sensitivity to atmospheric model resolution.

The remainder of this report is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the IFS and HadGEM3 atmosphere-only model configurations. Section 3 provides an overview of the experimental design, including the specification of time-varying surface boundary conditions and external climate forcings. Section 4 describes the data produced by each model and its availability to EERIE project partners. Section 5 provides a preliminary evaluation of the atmosphere-only simulations relative to reanalysis data and selected observations.

Atmosphere model	Horizontal resolution	Ensemble size	Period	Corresponding coupled models	Status
IFS	Tco1279 (~9 km)	1 member	1980-2023	IFS-NEMO IFS-FESOM	Complete
IFS	Tco399 (~28 km)	5 members			Complete
UM	N640 (~20 km)	1 member	1980-2023	HadGEM3-UM-NEMO	2014
UM	N216 (~60 km)	1 member			Complete

Table 1: Summary of EERIE atmosphere-only reference simulations.

2 Atmosphere model descriptions

2.1 ECMWF Integrated Forecasting System (IFS)

The atmosphere-only simulations described in this report are produced using a modified version of IFS Cycle 48r1 (ECMWF, 2024; Rackow et al., 2024), which is consistent with the atmospheric model component of the EERIE coupled models IFS-FESOM and IFS-NEMO (see deliverable 4.1). This configuration includes several modifications to the operational implementation of IFS cycle 48r1 developed as part of the [NextGEMS](#) project (Rackow et al., 2024). These include the activation of tracer mass-fixers to improve global energy and moisture conservation and parameter tuning to improve the top-of-the-atmosphere (TOA) radiation balance. One difference from the configuration described by Rackow et al., (2024) is that we do not reduce the magnitude of the parameterised

cloud-base mass flux, which has been shown to be beneficial in 4km IFS simulations (Becker et al. 2021). Instead, we adopt the standard operational settings for the IFS deep convection scheme, which provides superior performance for the atmospheric resolutions used within EERIE.

The atmospheric component of the IFS is based on a two-time-level semi-implicit, semi-Lagrangian dynamical core with computations alternated between spectral and cubic octahedral reduced Gaussian (TCo) grid-point representations each time step (Simmons et al. 1989; Hortal and Simmons, 1991; Ritchie et al. 1995; Temperton et al., 2001; Hortal, 2002; Diamantakis and Váňa, 2022). We use a time step of 450 seconds with the Tco1279 grid (~9 km resolution) and a time step of 900 seconds with the Tco399 grid (~28 km resolution). Both configurations use 137 vertical levels and, for computational efficiency, use 32-bit "single" precision for (almost) all floating point calculations (Váňa et al. 2017; Lang et al. 2021). We do not use any stochastic perturbations to parameterised model physics. Ensembles are generated by perturbing atmosphere initial conditions for January 1st 1980 following the same process that is applied in operational ECMWF ensemble forecasts. Perturbations are generated using a combination of singular vectors and the ERA5 ensemble of data assimilations (EDA), as described by Lock et al. (2019).

The IFS code used for the atmosphere-only and coupled simulations for EERIE is defined using the ifs-bundle tag "DE_CY48R1.0_EERIE_20240726", which includes among others the source code (ifs-source), data encoding (eccodes), as well as the tools to run the simulations (RAPS) and the output specification (RAPS, MultIO).

2.2 Met Office Unified Model (UM)

The atmosphere-only simulations described in this report are produced using a modified version of the HadGEM3-GC5 configuration (Xavier et al. in prep; named HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE here), which is consistent with the atmosphere component of the coupled model used in EERIE simulations (deliverable 4.1). In the UM atmospheric component, the standard atmospheric convection scheme in HadGEM3-GC5 has been replaced with the Convective Morphology (CoMorphA) scheme (Lavender et al., 2024; Daleu et al. 2022), which remains as a convective mass flux scheme but replaces the shallow, mid and deep convection of the standard convection scheme (Gregory and Rowntree, 1990).

The UM's ENDGame dynamical core uses a semi-implicit semi-Lagrangian formulation to solve the non-hydrostatic, fully compressible deep-atmosphere equations of motion (Wood et al., 2014). The model timestep is 900 seconds for the N216 grid (~60 km) and 600 seconds for the N640 grid (~20 km). Both configurations use 85 model levels in the vertical. There is only one parameter difference between the two model resolutions, "two_d_fsd_factor" (overall cloud inhomogeneity

parameter) is set to 1.62 for N216 and 1.61 for N640, settings chosen in the coupled model to tune the Top-of-Atmosphere (TOA) balance to close to zero (in a pre-industrial control simulation).

3 Experimental design

3.1 SST and sea ice boundary conditions

Time-evolving ocean and sea-ice boundary conditions in these atmosphere-only simulations are prescribed using high-resolution satellite-based estimates of sea surface temperature (SST) and sea-ice concentration (SIC). SSTs are specified using data from the European Space Agency Sea Surface Temperature Climate Change Initiative (ESA CCI SST version 3.0), which provides daily mean ocean temperatures representative of 20 cm depth from 1980 to present (Embury et al. 2024). Daily mean sea ice concentrations are specified using data from European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT) Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility (OSI-SAF). Specifically, we use the OSI-450 and OSI-430-b sea ice concentration products that are distributed alongside – and used as inputs for – the ESA CCI SST v3.0.1 analysis (Embury et al. 2024). These data were retrieved from Jasmin (Climate Data Record ([CDR](#)) for 1980-2021 and Intermediate Climate Data Record ([ICDR](#)) for 2022-2023) on a $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ latitude-longitude grid and then interpolated as required by each atmospheric model. For the IFS simulations, SST and sea-ice data were conservatively interpolated to the required cubic octahedral reduced Gaussian grid using the MIR software (Maciel et al. 2017).

Figure 1: Daily mean global SST anomalies from 1980 to present in different data sets.

Our choice of ESA CCI SST v3.0.1 was guided by our requirements for an observation-based multidecadal dataset with global coverage, high temporal frequency, high spatial resolution, consistency through time, and an accurate representation of climate variability and trends. Compared to previous versions, ESA CCI SST v3.0.1 has improved accuracy and temporal consistency, especially during the 1980s and early 1990s (Embury et al. 2024). For example, ESA CCI SST v3.0.1 does not exhibit spurious variability of daily mean global SST anomalies during the 1980s and early 1990s, which are evident in other SST data sets (figure 1).

Despite these improvements to data consistency, there are some characteristics of ESA CCI SST v3.0.1 that evolve with time. In particular, although the SST data is distributed on a $0.05^{\circ} \times 0.05^{\circ}$ grid, the feature resolution is typically lower than 15 km (Embury et al. 2024) and is generally lower during the earlier period due to lack of high-resolution satellite sensors (figure 2). Based on the time-evolution of spatial gradients in the ESA CCI SST v3.0.1 data set, we recommend that scientific analysis to understand the atmospheric response to mesoscale SST features in EERIE simulations should focus on the period after 1985.

It should be noted that this simulation design is essentially what is proposed for the atmosphere-only simulations in HighResMIP2 (Roberts et al., 2024), and hence this is an early test of that international effort.

Figure 2: ESA-CCI v3 SST for January 1st 1980 (left) and 2020 (right). The evolution of satellite observing technology means that feature resolution is generally lower during the earlier period of the dataset.

3.2 External forcings

External radiative forcings are generally specified following CMIP6/HighResMIP protocols (Eyring et al. 2016; Haarsma et al. 2016). However, there are some differences between model configurations, which are outlined below.

3.2.1 External forcings in IFS simulations

External forcings in the IFS are mostly specified as described in Roberts et al. (2018), with some modifications. In particular, tropospheric aerosols in IFS simulations are specified as time-evolving climatologies generated using methods developed within the [CONFESS](#) project (Stockdale et al 2022, Stockdale et al., 2024). These climatologies are derived from IFS simulations with prognostic atmospheric chemistry driven by CMIP6 emissions data, in which the atmospheric circulation is constrained to track the observed meteorological conditions as represented by the ERA5 reanalysis. Each climatology is representative of a 9-year running mean, which is sampled at 3-year intervals from 1975 to 2015. After 2015, climatologies are held constant such that recent changes in tropospheric aerosols are not represented. From 1980-2014, greenhouse gases (i.e. CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, CFC11 and CFC12), volcanic aerosols, ozone, and total solar irradiance are specified to follow CMIP6 historical data as described in Roberts et al. (2018). For the period after 2015, for which CMIP6 historical data are not available, we specify external forcings as follows: (i) greenhouse gases and ozone are specified to follow the SSP3-7.0 scenario, (ii) volcanic aerosol optical depths are held constant using a representative “no major emissions” year, and (iii) solar forcings are specified using the CMIP6 reference estimate of most likely solar activity from 2015 to 2300. Other external boundary conditions, including land surface properties, are specified as seasonally varying climatologies that do not evolve with time.

3.2.2 External forcings in Met Office simulations

Forcings used in the Met Office simulations are based on CMIP6 forcing datasets. Indeed, apart from aerosols and land surface properties, all other forcings are as used in the Met Office’s CMIP6 HighResMIP (Haarsma et al. 2016) simulations (Roberts et al. 2019), at least up to 2014 (the end of the historical period in CMIP6). The HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE model uses a prognostic aerosol scheme GLOMAP-mode (Mann et al. 2010) and appropriate aerosol emissions files as used in CMIP6 (previous HighResMIP simulations used a more idealised aerosol forcing). For the period 2015-2023, all forcings use the future scenario SSP2-4.5, as this was the best match to what has happened in that period. Land surface properties evolve annually (as well as seasonally) using the CMIP6 forcings.

4 Data availability

This section provides a summary of the data produced by the IFS and HadGEM3 atmosphere-only reference simulations described above.

4.1 ECMWF IFS data

IFS atmosphere-only simulations were run on the ECMWF supercomputer, where all outputs were written to disk within a [Fields Database \(FDB\)](#). All output variables (Table 1) are defined following [GRIB2](#) standards as encoded by [ecCodes](#) 2.36.1 with descriptions available in the [ECMWF parameter database](#). The choice of IFS output variables was guided by the EERIE Data Request but also constrained by the available disk space on the ECMWF supercomputer and EERIE collaboration platforms. The variables, frequencies, and resolutions of output data thus reflect a balance between outputs required for comprehensive process-based evaluation of weather and climate variability and efficient use of HPC resources and storage. Based on these considerations, data from IFS atmosphere-only simulations was output on both the native atmosphere model grid (either Tco1279 or Tco399) and a regular 0.25°x0.25° latitude-longitude grid to which they are regridded with conservative interpolation using [MIR](#) (Maciel et al. 2017). All variables are available as instantaneous values at 6-hourly intervals (or 6-hourly accumulations for fluxes), daily means, and monthly means. Fluxes are accumulated online from model step data and thus derived average rates are exact. Daily and monthly means for other fields are computed online from hourly native resolution data using [MultIO](#) (Sarmany et al. 2024).

Surface/single-level fields	Accumulated/flux fields
2 metre temperature	Total precipitation
2 metre dewpoint temperature	Convective precipitation
2 metre specific humidity	Snowfall
10 metre wind speed	Evaporation
10 metre zonal wind	Zonal surface stress
10 metre meridional wind	Meridional surface stress
Instantaneous 10 metre wind gust	Runoff
Boundary layer height	Surface runoff
Sea ice area fraction	Sub-surface runoff
Sea surface temperature	Latent heat flux
Mean sea level pressure	Sensible heat flux
Snow depth	Surface net shortwave radiation
Skin temperature	Surface net shortwave radiation, clear sky
Surface pressure	Surface net long-wave radiation
Soil moisture on 4 levels	Surface net long-wave radiation, clear sky
Soil temperature on 4 levels	Surface long-wave radiation downwards
Maximum 10 metre wind gust	Surface short-wave radiation downwards
Maximum 2 metre temperature	Top incident short-wave radiation
Minimum 2 metre temperature	Top net short-wave radiation
High cloud cover	Top net short-wave radiation, clear sky

Medium cloud cover	Top net long-wave radiation
Low cloud cover	Top net long-wave radiation, clear sky
Total cloud cover	
Total column cloud ice water	Pressure level fields
Total column cloud liquid water	Geopotential
Total column water	Temperature
Total column vertically-integrated water vapour	Zonal wind
Significant wave height	Meridional wind
Mean zero-crossing wave period	Vertical velocity
Mean wave direction	Relative humidity
Mean wave period	Specific humidity
Peak wave period	

Table 2: Available output variables from IFS atmosphere-only simulations. 3D fields are available on the following pressure levels: 1000, 925, 850, 700, 600, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 20, 10, 30, 5, 1 hPa.

For collaboration within the EERIE project, a large fraction of IFS regridded output is now available on the [Levante](#) and [JASMIN](#) computing platforms. We have so-far prioritised sharing data on the regular 0.25°x0.25° latitude-longitude grid. In addition, a small subset of native resolution output has also been made available for those calculations that require the highest possible horizontal resolution. The main starting point for data access on these platforms are the intake catalogues described on the [EERIE project GitHub repository](#). The recent work on “eerie.cloud” (Savage & Wachsmann 2023; Wachsmann 2024) allows users to [browse](#) the available datasets and create interactive visualisations (e.g. Figure 3).

Work is ongoing to archive all native resolution IFS data to the ECMWF operational Meteorological Archival and Retrieval System ([MARS](#)), where it will be publicly available under a new EERIE data class (“ed”). The MARS client supports retrieval at native model resolutions or regridding to a wide variety of horizontal grids and will provide a long-term solution for users to interact with the EERIE IFS atmosphere-only simulations.

Figure 3: Instantaneous 10 metre wind gust speed on the Tco1279 (~9 km) model native grid as visualised by the interactive DKRZ “gridlook” application.

4.2 Met Office UM data

The data produced from the Met Office simulations is as agreed for the atmospheric part of the EERIE coupled simulations, with some additional high frequency variables produced. Due to resourcing issues, currently this data is primarily only available from the Met Office data archive, with small subsets being provided on JASMIN by request. In due course we plan to standardise the data format (CMORise the data) and make much more of it generally available.

5 Preliminary evaluation

This section provides a preliminary assessment of atmosphere-only simulations evaluated against the ERA5 atmospheric reanalysis (Hersbach et al. 2020) and selected observational datasets. These comparisons focus on the data from Tco399 and Tco1279 IFS simulations, with some limited comparisons with data from the HadGEM3 model.

5.1 Model biases and trends

Both models at their respective resolutions accurately capture long-term trends and interannual variability in global mean 2m temperature and net TOA radiation balance (figure 4), which partly reflects the strong constraint from the specified SST boundary conditions. Unlike the available UM

simulation, the IFS-based data do not capture the stronger warming trend from ~2015 onwards. This may reflect differences in the prescribed time-varying forcings (e.g. aerosols).

For precipitation, the IFS simulations agree well with ERA5, which may reflect the similarity of the underlying model used to generate the IFS-based ERA5 global reanalysis. The UM simulations have slightly higher global mean precipitation but the trends are similar. The evaluation of precipitation trends is difficult due to the relatively low confidence in ERA5 precipitation and the diverging observational precipitation datasets. GPM-IMERG and GPCP disagree both on the average level of precipitation and the temporal evolution.

Long-term trends and interannual variability are also well captured in the free troposphere, as shown in Hovmöller plots of 500 hPa temperature anomalies (figure 5). For example, these plots demonstrate that IFS atmosphere-only simulations are capable of simulating temperature anomalies associated with major ENSO events (such as during 1998 and 2016).

One notable deficiency in the IFS Tco399 simulations is a $\sim 1.5 \text{ W/m}^2$ negative bias in global mean net TOA radiation balance. In contrast, global mean net TOA radiation fluxes in Tco1279 simulations are in good agreement with estimates from the ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al. 2020) and CERES observations (Loeb et al. 2018). These differences in planetary energy balance are a consequence of differences in cloud properties, which are sensitive to horizontal resolution (figure 4). The good agreement at Tco1279 is a consequence of tuning cloud-related parameters to improve the agreement with observations at higher resolutions (Rackow et al. 2024). For consistency, we have retained the same cloud parameters at both resolutions, despite the resulting $\sim 1.5 \text{ W/m}^2$ negative bias in global mean net TOA radiation balance in the Tco399 configuration. This global mean bias has a very limited impact in the lower-resolution IFS atmosphere-only simulations due to the strong constraint from the imposed SSTs. However, we note that a similar magnitude bias would negatively impact coupled ocean-atmosphere climate simulations. For this reason, we would recommend re-tuning cloud parameters before running multi-decadal coupled simulations with the Tco399 configuration of the IFS used in EERIE.

Figure 4: Global mean (or quasi-global mean) time series of 2m temperature, TOA net radiation balance, total precipitation, and total cloud cover in atmosphere-only simulations. IFS simulations are tco399 & tco1279, UM simulations n216 and n640. Time series are plotted as annual means and are compared to equivalent data from ERA5 (black), GPM-IMERG (brown), GPCP (pink) and CERES (grey).

Seasonal biases in zonal mean temperature and zonal mean zonal wind are shown in figures 6 and 7, respectively. Consistent with previous multidecadal atmosphere-only simulations with the IFS (Roberts et al. 2018), biases in the troposphere show limited sensitivity to changes in horizontal resolution. However, there is some evidence for a larger magnitude cold bias in the stratosphere (~ 50 hPa) in the higher resolution Tco1279 simulations. This is likely a consequence of discretization errors in the vertical advection associated with vertically propagating gravity waves, which becomes more problematic at higher horizontal resolutions (Polichtchouk et al. 2019). However, these errors are substantially reduced compared to previous versions of the IFS used in CMIP6/HighResMIP1. This can be attributed to the higher-order vertical interpolation in the semi-lagrangian advection scheme and an increased number of vertical levels used in these simulations, both of which alleviate temperature biases related to the vertical propagation of gravity waves (Polichtchouk et al. 2019; Lang et al. 2021).

Figure 5: Time-evolution of zonal mean temperature anomalies at 500 hPa relative to their own climatology, for ERA5 (top) and the IFS atmosphere-only simulations at tco1279 (middle) and tco399 (bottom) resolution.

Figure 6: Seasonal mean biases for zonal mean temperature relative to ERA5 for IFS Tco1279 (top) and IFS Tco399 (bottom) calculated over the period 1980-2023.

Figure 7: Seasonal mean biases for zonal mean zonal wind relative to ERA5 for IFS Tco1279 (top) and IFS Tco399 (bottom) calculated over the period 1980-2023.

5.2 Eddy composites

In this section, we demonstrate that IFS Tco399 and Tco1279 simulations are able to simulate a local atmospheric response to SST anomalies associated with ocean mesoscale eddies. To do this, we combine observation-based estimates of ocean eddy locations with a lagrangian composite analysis of high-pass filtered model fields. These composites provide an estimate of the average impact of an ocean eddy on the atmospheric field of interest.

To begin, eddies are identified using [py-eddy-tracker](#) (Mason et al. 2014; Pegliasco et al. 2022) applied to the [AVISO](#) sea surface height dataset. We then construct composites from data on a $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ latitude-longitude grid after high-pass filtering using [GCM-filters](#) (Loose et al. 2022) with a spatially-varying length scale of 20 times the local Rossby radius. The resulting length scale is 2 to 4 times larger than the average eddy diameter in the Southern Ocean. Composites are constructed by averaging data within a $2.5^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$ region around each sampled eddy location. We focus on Southern Ocean eddies, which have a relatively uniform size and shape such that the resulting composites are relatively symmetrical.

Figure 8 shows composite means of SST, 2m temperature, latent heat flux, and total precipitation calculated from 1,204,617 snapshots of anticyclonic eddies tracked during 2021 between 25°S and 60°S . Starting on the first column from the left, we see that the typical anticyclonic eddy in the Southern Ocean is about 0.25 K warmer than its surroundings. Reassuringly, the eddy features in

AVISO are associated with warm-core structures in ESA CCI SST v3.0. For SST composites the difference (bottom) between data from IFS Tco1279 (top) and IFS Tco399 (middle) is ~ 0.02 K, a relative difference of 8%. This difference is a consequence of interpolation from the original grid, to the intermediate IFS grid, and finally to the regular grid for composite analysis. Although the SST imprint of Southern Ocean eddies is slightly better resolved at Tco1279, the relevant features are still adequately represented after interpolation via the Tco399 atmosphere model grid.

Figure 8: Eddy composite means derived from 1,204,617 snapshots of anticyclonic eddies identified from AVISO during 2021 in the Southern Ocean between 25°S and 60°S. Shown are the composites for IFS Tco1279 (top) and IFS Tco399 (middle) resolution, with their difference in the bottom row.

We also see a clear imprint of mesoscale ocean eddies on surface air temperature and latent heat fluxes, although the 2m temperature response is only ~20% of the magnitude of the corresponding SST composites and thus small compared to the total day-to-day atmospheric variability. The impact of resolution is similar to that seen for SST, with Tco1279 composites being about 10% stronger than Tco399. Interestingly, the resolution impact on precipitation composites seems to be reversed, with the response about ~10% stronger in Tco399 simulations. However, given the noise in the precipitation composite differences, this may reflect sampling uncertainty. This preliminary analysis indicates that the local atmosphere response to ocean eddies is generally rather weak and similar in IFS simulations with a horizontal resolution of ~25 km and ~9 km. It will be interesting to compare the same diagnostics applied to the EERIE coupled simulations to evaluate the role of an interactive ocean on the strength of the atmospheric response.

6 Summary

This report has described the EERIE atmosphere-only reference simulations, including an overview of the experimental design, model configurations, and data availability. Simulations have been conducted with two resolutions of the ECMWF IFS (~28 km and ~9 km) and Met Office HadGEM3 (~60 km and ~20 km) atmosphere models. Ocean and sea-ice boundary conditions are specified using high-resolution satellite-based estimates of daily-mean sea surface temperature and sea-ice concentration. Other than their treatment of ocean and sea-ice boundary conditions, the higher-resolution configurations of IFS and HadGEM3 described here are scientifically identical to the atmosphere components of the corresponding EERIE coupled simulations. A preliminary evaluation has demonstrated that the EERIE atmosphere-only simulations accurately capture long-term trends and interannual variability in several climate metrics and an exploratory Lagrangian composite analysis of ~25 km and ~9 km IFS simulations indicates that both configurations have sufficient horizontal resolution to capture a local atmospheric response to SST anomalies associated with ocean mesoscale eddies. These experiments will be exploited in other EERIE work packages in combination with EERIE coupled simulations and other idealised atmosphere-only experiments to provide insights into the impacts of ocean coupling, atmospheric resolution, and the role of the ocean mesoscale for weather and climate variability.

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